

New Machine Learning-Based Tool, CyFi, Uses Sentinel-2 Imagery to Enable HAB Monitoring in Small Inland Water Bodies

Fig. 1. A series of satellite images contrasting sensor resolution — medium-resolution (Sentinel-2, 10 m, Right) imagery that can resolve small lakes vs coarse (Sentinel-3, 300 m, Left) imagery that cannot.

Current efforts to monitor harmful algal blooms (HABs) face a challenge: an entire class of water bodies we need to watch — small lakes, reservoirs, and rivers — are precisely where our tools are constrained. Chlorophyll estimates from Sentinel-3 satellite data have been used extensively in large lakes, coastal, and marine environments, but the spatial resolution (300 m) cannot resolve smaller inland waters of a few hundred acres (100 hectares) or less (Fig. 1). Conversely, traditional in-situ buoys, Imaging FlowCytobots, and

manual field sample collection provide point-based precision, yet are limited in coverage and frequency by costs, logistics, staff and volunteer availability, and lab capacity. This gap in observational capability has left resource managers with incomplete situational awareness, especially in regions with thousands of small water bodies that have significant recreational, drinking water, and ecological value.

A new model for satellite-based wide area monitoring closes this gap. Cyanobacteria Finder (CyFi) is an open-

source Python tool that combines medium-resolution (10–30m) Sentinel-2 satellite data with a computationally efficient tree-based machine learning model to infer cyanobacteria density and assign severity categories that align with WHO guidelines[1]. There is also support for optional imagery overlays via the CyFi Explorer, which visually contextualizes bloom extent around the point estimates in small water bodies (Fig. 2). CyFi’s methodology has been published in the Proceedings of the Python in Science Conference[2], and the

Fig. 2. Detection of HAB in a small lake in California, shown in the CyFi Explorer, which is a feature in the open-source CyFi package[3–4].

Fig. 3. A comparison chart showing CyFi vs. CyAN bloom detection accuracy in terms of true positives and true negatives for a test dataset covering 756 ground-sampled data points across the U.S. A true positive (bloom presence) is where cyanobacteria density > 10000 cells·mL⁻¹.

open-source software package is publicly available[3].

CyFi's development followed a replicable pattern of crowdsourced innovation, then experimentation, validation, and tool development. It began with an open machine learning competition — the *Tick Tick Bloom: Harmful Algal Bloom Detection Challenge* run by DrivenData and funded by NASA, with collaboration from NOAA, EPA, USGS, DOD's Defense Innovation Unit, Berkeley AI Research, and Microsoft AI for Earth. The community-driven phase (900 submissions from 115 teams) yielded practical methodologies that generalized across a wide range of inland environments. A subsequent model experimentation phase iterated on approaches from winning models and restructured the code into a robust, configurable, and runnable pipeline. In parallel, DrivenData conducted user interviews with water quality managers in several U.S. states. Insights from these interviews were used to align CyFi's design with decision-making workflows, ensuring its outputs were not only scientifically robust but also operationally useful. This development arc — from competition to practitioner feedback to a deployment-ready open-source package — helped to balance technical rigor with real-world utility.

The core innovation in CyFi is the way machine learning infers signals that the satellite itself cannot explicitly measure. Sentinel-2 lacks the narrow

spectral bands that directly isolate cyanobacteria pigments such as phycocyanin, yet it provides imagery at spatial resolutions that can resolve smaller water bodies. For the competition, a novel dataset of over 23,000 in situ cyanobacteria measurements was compiled from the 48 contiguous U.S. states and is now publicly available through the NASA SeaBASS archive[5]. Through training, the CyFi model learned to translate combinations of broadband *reflectances into estimates of bloom severity*. When benchmarked against established tools like the Cyanobacteria Index (CyAN), developed for Sentinel-3 data (300 m resolution), CyFi achieves comparable presence/absence accuracy while covering an order of magnitude more water bodies by leveraging higher spatial-resolution imagery (Fig. 3).

The potential benefits of CyFi for a regional monitoring program include: adding spatio-temporal depth to HAB detections from field samples and monitoring buoys; extending the reach of monitoring systems by identifying blooms that are otherwise undetected because they fall outside the resolution, geographic area, or frequency of current sampling regimes; providing context that can be used to prioritize/optimize field sampling and the placement of in situ systems; and providing an extra level of regional HAB awareness that can be fed into dashboards and advisory systems.

Operationalizing tools like CyFi high-

lights challenges common to machine-learning systems. Model outputs may need adjustment for environments they have not been trained on; while training datasets are extensive, they may not be fully representative of local conditions. Accordingly, practitioners are advised to pair CyFi predictions with targeted ground-truthing to calibrate models for their region as part of the CyFi adoption process.

Advances in machine learning and remote sensing are steadily improving both spatial and temporal resolution of our observational systems, and each advance creates opportunities to improve environmental monitoring and decision-making. CyFi exemplifies this progression; its data-driven approach to HAB monitoring extends the observational reach to small inland water bodies while preserving rigor and relevance to water-quality management.

Acknowledgements

The project was supported by funding from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Science Mission Directorate's Earth Science, Applied Sciences, Health and Air Quality, and the NASA Prizes, Challenges, and Crowdsourcing Programs.

References

1. World Health Organization 2003. *Guidelines for safe recreational water environments. Volume 1: Coastal and fresh waters*. World Health Organization, Geneva. 253 p.
2. Dorne E et al. 2024. *Proc Python Sci Conf 23:154–173*. doi.org/10.25080/PDHHK7238
3. DrivenData 2023. *CyFi: Cyanobacteria Finder*. <https://cyfi.drivendata.org/>
4. DrivenData 2023. *CyFi Explorer*. <https://cyfi.drivendata.org/explorer/>
5. Gupta S & Gelbart E 2024. *Cyanobacteria Aggregated Manual Labels (CAML) experiment*. SeaBASS. <https://seabass.gsfc.nasa.gov/experiment/CAML>

Authors

Emily Dorne, DrivenData, United States

Email corresponding author:
emily@drivendata.org

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19045768>